

**GULISTAN
STATE
UNIVERSITY**

PERSPECTIVES OF PHILOLOGY AND PRACTICAL POSSIBILITIES OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

**PROCEEDINGS
OF THE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE**

GULISTAN, OCTOBER 16-17, 2024

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KAZAN FEDERAL UNIVERSITY (RUSSIA)

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OLIV TA'LIM, FAN VA INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI

GULISTON DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI (O'ZBEKISTON)

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VA CHET TILLAR O'QITISHNING
AMALIY IMKONIYATLARI**

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To‘plamga kiritilgan ma‘ruza tezislarning mazmuni, undagi ma‘lumotlar va me‘yoriy hujjatlarning to‘g‘riligi hamda fikr-mulohazalar, keltirilgan takliflarga mualliflarning o‘zlari mas‘uldirlar.

PEDAGOGICAL ROLE OF WORLD SCIENCE FICTION: PARADOXES AND IMPLEMENTATION

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Abstract. It is quite clear that art was bound to respond to the ongoing changes in life. And so it happened. In literature, a direction of science fiction appeared and became stronger, designed to express the inexhaustible desire of people to look beyond the horizons of knowledge, understand the future and somehow plan it. In science, this is called the principle of anticipatory reflection.

Keywords: fantastic, science fiction, fantasy, education, reflection, future.

Introduction. The fantastic is the oldest and integral component of art, which has a desire for the widespread use of conditional forms of depicting reality, creates its own system of fantastic images, present in all its areas where the modeling mechanism is used. In modern culture, fantasy occupies an important place due to its multifunctional manifestations, as it is a kind of synthesis of intellectual, artistic and aesthetic values that determine the degree of its impact on many aspects of people's lives [Berdyaev 2000: 28]. At the same time, it is important to take into account that human psychology is initially aimed at the unusual, the impossible, i.e., the fantastic. Less than half a century ago, the first manned flight into space took place. Retreating in time, this event seems to be an increasingly significant milestone in the history of our planet. Now it becomes especially important to understand the vector of the further movement of human thought and to find those criteria that will allow us to give a correct assessment of the past. After all, only now we are beginning to realize how critical the past century turned out to be for our entire civilization. The man, who until then had been crawling blindly on the surface of the planet, suddenly straightened up and with incredible speed broke the shackles of the earth's gravity. The inexhaustibility of the world opened before him with his own eyes, giving previously unimaginable opportunities. Naturally, the reckless striving for the future is a systemic quality of young people who carelessly feel the ocean of long life in front of them. An excess of strength and impressionability allows you to build the desired image of the future and, with all the ardor of romantic enthusiasm, strive for its implementation. High-quality fiction helps structure expectations and vague dreams, better understand your own preferences. It awakens not only feelings, concretizing them, but also thought. Of course, not only young people love science fiction, but people of all ages think about the future. The very emergence of science fiction is an important step in the development of mass consciousness. The plasticity of the youthful psyche and its openness to all manifestations of life make any influence on it full of special meaning [Bern 2002: 350].

Problem. Meanwhile, *at school, nothing is said about science fiction in literature classes, although the books most read by schoolchildren are of this genre.* It turns out that an essential and, most importantly, promising part of youth culture does not fit in with the corresponding school subject. But it is our children who will build the future, choose the ways of its development. And we will have to put up with their choice one way or another, because the younger generation always has an advantage in time [Boldyrev 2000: 101]. Wouldn't it be better to direct the appropriate interest of a young person already at school age? After all, if interest is arbitrary, then arbitrary and, consequently, more superficial results in society as a whole. Now young people read mostly science fiction, in which there are no clear moral guidelines and a minimal idea of connection with real life. Passion for the genre turns into a distraction from the problems of the aggressive outside world, without causing a desire to change the existing situation. This is evidenced by the success of the fantasy direction, as well as space opera and cyberpunk. Fantasy is a fantasy tale in which, as a rule, an invincible hero with a sword acts in the world of magic and witchcraft. Often he ends up in a magical world from our world; this happens by chance and is not explained in any way [Britikov 2000: 395]. The action develops according to the laws of the action movie, respectively, and the behavior of the characters. R.

Tolkien's work, who created a huge world with a long history and a special language, is considered a fantasy classic. The movement of the so-called "Tolkienists" vividly demonstrates all the stages of the consequences of mass hypnosis, provided by a talentedly written work, which has almost no points of contact with objective reality. The main character is constantly persuaded to cooperate by light and dark forces. If in the classics of the genre the choice in favor of the forces of light was unambiguous, then in the last decade the motifs of the "gray" path leading to perfect self-sufficiency of a person independent of anyone began to sound much more often. Moreover, the motives for choosing the "black" path have appeared and strengthened, and the very idea of good and evil is blurred not only on the example of particulars, but also in general in the concept of the author (N.D. Perumov, S.V. Lukyanenko). In the work, built on the principle of a space opera, the magical surroundings are replaced by a clumsily drawn technogenic one. Cyberpunk is characterized by even greater manufacturability and depressive presentation of the material. In fact, we are dealing with a mirror reflection of the collisions taking place in our country. The collapse of the moral core is a welcome phenomenon for the soulless business world, preoccupied with momentary personal gain. Ethical relativism combined with escapism is the surest means for leveling islands of independently seeking thought.

Discussion. It is possible and necessary *to draw the attention of the younger generation to the best examples of world fiction, but it is precisely scientific, with a clear spatio-temporal plot and clear goals of presentation, since such material can appeal not only to the soul, but also to the intellect of the young reader.* Much to our regret, modern literary criticism makes it possible to quickly get an idea of such "writers" as Eduard Limonov or Venedikt Erofeev, while a huge layer of such literature is actually not in demand. The most serious futurological research by deeply and multifaceted people, the formulation of really important and urgent problems of the present and the future - all this is left out of modern science and, accordingly, school teaching. At school, the insignificant and hardly readable N.I. Tryapkin and V.S. Rozov are studied. Speaking of the literary tradition, we will strictly distinguish fantasy as a method of integral construction from fantasy as a subordinate device. N.V. Gogol's nose leads an independent life, but this does not mean that the author of "The Nose" can be written down as the predecessor of A.R. Belyaev with his "Professor Dowell's Head". Fiction in the works of M.A. Bulgakov is also by no means self-sufficient, although, for example, "Heart of a Dog" formally echoes the work of the same Belyaev. Meanwhile, many of the "stories about the extraordinary" by I.A. Efremov, despite the minimum of a fantastic element, quite fit the definition of fantasy. Without a fantastic idea, albeit a very small one, these stories do not exist, while Bulgakov's works may well do without a fictional one. Working with a fantastic work at a school lesson is a very special activity that requires the teacher to be ready to conduct a conversation along several lines at the same time - scientific, technical, social, ethical, aesthetic and philosophical.

Why is it so important to appeal specifically to the global science fiction tradition? In general, world literature is characterized by a special humanism and the posing of the most profound questions of life. Of course, there are also negative examples. Thus, saturated with original technical ideas, a significant part of American fiction is completely alienated from man himself. Rare upsurges of the spirit in it express a random phenomenon and are not conditioned by anything other than the personal preference of the character. The man in the mass of works is either busy solving some ingenious technical problem or "galactic" politics, and his character, manners, desires and ideas about life are fully consistent with the modern Western American standard. It is clear that against the backdrop of a rapidly changing life, such a flat understanding of the man of the future is unacceptable. But for the most part, in world science fiction, the problem of man is in the foreground and it is expressed in many ways. The heroes are forced to solve complex moral problems in the course of action, for which a significant baggage of sciences is involved, not only technical, but also humanitarian. Even Belyaev, aware of the incompleteness of his work, pointed out that the content of science fiction should be new social relations and an attempt to portray the people of the new world [Karmin 2004: 903]. The dream of applying scientific achievements to the transformation of nature, society and man himself is the essence of real science fiction, closely connected with the tradition of the philosophy of cosmism. The increase in the intellectual complexity of life steadily requires the highest subtlety of moral decisions. A radical bias towards extensive knowledge and the exchange of superficial information led to totalitarianism, on the

one hand, and demagogic pluralism, on the other. Correspondingly, the task of school literature is to contribute to the deepening of the impression of what is read and the ability to reflect on what is happening in life, to build up from the particular, understanding the whole. The best works of world science fiction carry a universal ideological load, their versatility and the presence of a core moral principle are able to play a huge pedagogical role.

Now let's talk about specific authors whose work best meets the currently ignored needs of the young soul. First of all, this is I.A. Efremov, whose works are unusually rich and multi-vector. The images of Efremov's heroes are an unprecedented phenomenon in world literature. These people of the future (and we are now talking only about the fantastic works of the master) are endowed with the gift of a deep understanding of the laws of the universe and their place in it. Thought - word - deed. Such a triad is the basis of the spiritual development of man, in which, due to the natural correlation of positive qualities, there are more, otherwise he would not have taken place as a species. The dialectic of the deep foundations of being is revealed by the author in each episode, which gives rise to a feeling of completeness and solidity of the text. Being at the same time a major paleontologist, the writer asserted the unity of evolutionary mechanisms. At the biological level, those species that were less dependent on the environment succeeded. Man in this sense is universal. But he must be just as universal psychologically, not mindlessly dissolving in the accompanying social conditions, but consciously understanding their limits and conditionality. An individual who has completely given his "I" to the surrounding life is a dead end of development, changes in the world will psychologically break him, just as a narrowly adapted animal will die when living conditions change in its habitat. A person is not only the sum of knowledge, but the most complex architecture of feelings, but the development of mental and psychic forces will be fully developed only against the background of physical health, because the flame of intense thought and vivid feelings cannot blaze in a paper cup. Beauty is not a personal arbitrary preference, but the objective expediency of this or that construction, and the consciousness of the infinity of space and time is a necessary component of a fruitful creative process. The universe is necessarily inhabited, because the appearance of man is a consequence of the laws of the development of matter, which are uniform in the observed space. A huge role on this most difficult path belongs to a woman. Efremov bowed before the feminine. A woman is an inspirer and protector, and the beautiful is always more complete in a woman and more honed in her. The ascent of any society inevitably begins with the exaltation of woman; where the feminine principle is oppressed or likened to the masculine, degradation sets in. The gallery of "Efremov's women", written out with great love and respect, deserves a separate place in literary criticism. Strong and cheerful, devoted and fearless, such women can create a space around them that cleanses the noosphere. As you can see, even a simple enumeration of Efremov's conclusions arising from one another takes up a considerable amount of space. The writer was all focused on the future, but he clearly understood that only on the basis of historical memory is a viable construction possible. He foresaw the inevitable development of the third signal system (intuition) - an analogue of the starship "direct beam" with their common ability to instantly achieve the desired result. Distinguishing connections between phenomena that are outwardly separated from each other, understanding the enormous forces contained in a person, heroic realism and romance in the depiction of characters are characteristic of the work of Ivan Efremov.

The fantastic stories of V.P. Krapivin, the living patriarch of children's literature and teacher, the founder of the famous children's detachment "Carabella", have a similar power of persuasiveness. Here are the lines from the charter of the detachment: "I will fight with any injustice, meanness and cruelty, wherever I meet them. I will not wait for someone else to stand up for the truth before me. If I ever get scared, I won't back down. Courage is when a person is afraid and still does not turn off the road..." The most serious problems of childhood, namely growing up, socialization and interaction with the world of adults, are revealed in Krapivin's stories with especially poignant force and accuracy. Krapivin asks the question: why does the modern school value and form only two properties in students: not getting bad marks and being obedient? Is this its high purpose? Does society, first and foremost, need unreasoning executors, cogs and bolts? No need to adapt to reality. We need to change it. This is the basis of the Krapivin worldview. Addressed to children, such an understanding of life encounters the fierce resistance of those adults for whom children are an eternal

hindrance to a non-committal existence. The cycle "In the Depths of the Great Crystal" contains the same life-affirming beginning of awareness of the openness, infinity of the world. The idea of the Great Crystal with the Road between the edges is an external reflection of the importance of mastering the space of one's soul. It is not surprising that it is children, not constrained by prejudices and stereotypes, who become the heralds of this infinity, navigators along the various facets of the Crystal, and certain changes in the vast world depend on them. The deep interconnectedness of events, sensitivity to the "moments of truth" - these acupuncture points of life - are in full accordance with the spatial "transition points" and the physical overcoming of the universal expanses.

But these children, who freely walk around the neighborhood and are friends with the stars, are defenseless and vulnerable, like any other children, and even more so, because their unusualness is a source of rejection by adults and many peers. Childhood protection, special sensitivity to the unusual abilities of children is the basis of humane pedagogy, now proclaimed by Sh.A. Amonashvili. The work of Krapivin, with his beating nerve of a vulnerable child's soul, fully corresponds to these ideas. The moral purity and fearlessness of the "Krapivin boys" is akin to the energetic charm and selfless firmness of the "Efremov women". These guys, who discovered in themselves those very Efremov abilities of the "direct beam", contain the future of the universe. The future needs people who can think and feel in cosmic terms. And we need young people who have the experience of a genuine, spiritual life. Books by Commander Krapivin increase the immunity of the heart - the last barrier to the muddy flow of the cheeky ideology of the consumer society.

The early fiction of V.V. Golovachev is imbued with a whole garland of unique ideas, fused together with the original figures of people of the future. The characters of purposeful, strong and generous rescuers and stellar border guards, who go through the realization of the inexhaustibility and mystery of the cosmos, discovering their own reserves, involuntarily cause a desire to imitate. The eternal questions of love, duty, friendship and the boundaries of an adequate response to aggression are posed by the writer with all the sharpness. The concepts of cosmoethics, universal ecology and tolerance for other existence are central in such novels as "Relic", "Black Man", "Requiem for a Time Machine" ... The heroes of these and a number of other works have virtues and abilities that far exceed our reality. But this does not make them "supermen", all abilities with the prefix "super" are only a necessary condition for solving the most difficult problems of humanity's survival in space. The heroes of Golovachev subtly listen to the melody of what is happening, and their lyricism and diverse knowledge do not in the least interfere with the speed of thought and action. A special role in the public organization is occupied by SEKON - the service of Social and Ethical Control and Observation (an analogue of the Efremov Academy of Woe and Joy). Soethic experts have the right to "veto" in the development and implementation of certain decisions, whose ethical value seems to them doubtful. Golovachev visibly demonstrated that the townsfolk are doomed to wallow in the virtuality created by them or imposed from outside. Easily accessible material goods in the world of Golovachev's future did not solve the existential problem of man, but only highlighted it more clearly. The whole Universe should become the home of the renewed humanity, for which it is necessary to know ourselves and respect the secrets of the cosmos. For us, standing on the threshold of a technological revolution, this approach seems to be the only possible one.

The stylistic merits of these writers are also characteristic. Efremov's language is thick and heavy, but surprisingly proportional, like the Doric columns of the Parthenon. This is the weight of a gold nugget. Chased formulations are proportionately built and balanced. Efremov owns the word, like a diamond chisel, and with this chisel he grinds a convex image of a perfect world on a druse of minerals. Krapivin's language is completely different. But, as one Ephraim hero said: "The shades of beauty are infinitely diverse - this is the wealth of the world." The main thing is that the measure is observed. For every detail and small private detail, Krapivin finds a surprisingly capacious word that flows into the general narrative in the only possible way. This is not heavy gold, but transparent crystal. The lightness and apparent simplicity of Krapivin's language resembles an airier version of "laconism and dynamics of Pushkin's prose". Golovachev's language is unique in its own way. In world literature, a special place is given to landscape, portrait and psychological

characteristics; the descriptions of Leo Tolstoy, Theodore Dreiser and others, for all their outward differences, are outstanding facts of mastery of the word and demonstrate an amazing interaction between the power of impression and the conscious clarity of its expression [Cayua 2006: 161]. Golovachev went even further - he achieved amazing results in describing cosmic cataclysms, unusual states of matter or consciousness, unlike anything human. That is, he pushed the boundaries of the imagination, penetrating with the scalpel of the word into the most exotic depths of the universe.

Conclusion. The presented authors are triune in the essence of the impact on the reader. However, each one has a different mindset. The hypostasis of Efremov is an aspiration to the heights of the spirit. Hypostasis Krapivin - immersion in the transparent depths of the soul. The hypostasis of Golovachev is the disclosure of the entire breadth of the field of activity of the creative intellect and will. Writers offer hypotheses that will interest "techies", pose problems close to the humanities, and fascinate with the beauty of the style. The modernity and timeliness of their works is great not only in content, but also in form, to which schoolchildren pay attention in the first place. Let us remember that the passive-contemplative attitude of many children to reality with attempts to hide from it is the result of the ideological inertia of adults. And episodic indignation at today's life in the family or school is perceived by adolescents with condescending smiles. Because such indignation is spontaneous and, at best, calls to the past. But the return never reaches the goal. And young people always look to the future. And if a positive image of the future is not formed in time, another image will take its place, which will grow into an unconscious conviction that we are waiting for some catastrophes, wars with cyborgs or life in the matrix. And once the verdict is signed, everything is possible. And at the same time, nothing is needed... Two extremes that merge in the denial of the original fruitfulness of life. But man must always be on the threshold of the new, because he himself is new every moment. And only the fire of thought and a vivid feeling can form the image of the future.

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LANGUAGE, TEXT AND SPEECH ANALYSIS: UNLOCKING THE SECRETS OF HUMAN COMMUNICATION

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Annotation: article provides an overview of the field of language, text, and speech analysis, highlighting its importance, key methods, and applications. It explores how researchers analyze these aspects of human communication to gain valuable insights into human behavior, cognition, and social dynamics.

Keywords: analysis, text analysis, speech analysis, natural language processing (NLP), computational linguistics, corpus linguistics, discourse analysis, pragmatics, semantics, phonetics, prosody, sentiment analysis, topic modelling, machine learning.

Introduction: Language is the cornerstone of human interaction, allowing us to share thoughts, emotions, and information. Every day, we engage in complex acts of communication, leaving a trail of linguistic data in the form of text and speech. Analyzing this data can provide profound insights into our society, culture, and even our individual minds. The fields of language, text, and speech analysis delve into this rich tapestry of human expression, employing a variety of methods and tools to unlock its secrets.

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